

Least Squares Based Filtering Method for Missouri University of Science & Technology Reactor Criticality Assessment

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ABSTRACT

Criticality safety experiments were performed at Missouri University of Science & Technology Reactor (MSTR) in the summer of 2025. To perform effective analysis of a nuclear reactor at critical ($k_{\text{eff}}=1$), data collected from sensors must be processed and assessed to determine when power is approximately stable. A method to classify critical states using least-squares regression and threshold values is developed and applied to MSTR power data from experimentation to produce a group of 60 second 'near critical' windows to serve as test cases for criticality assessment. Samples were analyzed by performing regression on reactor power transformed to a logarithmic space. Threshold values of $\pm 1.30e-4$ were used to classify critical events resulting in a capture rate of 39.3% from MSTR linear power channel data. The highest-performing classified critical state resulted in a first-order regression coefficient of $3.43e-10$ and a normalized residual of $1.02e-7$, implying highly stable reactor power and minimal detector noise effects.

Keywords: nuclear reactor, criticality, regression, classification

1. INTRODUCTION

Nuclear reactors are complex systems which tend to be operated using explicit, prescribed states in order to ease operations, reduce the risk of transient effects, and produce more physically describable system behavior. One of the most important states of nuclear reactor operation is the critical state in which the effective multiplication factor, k_{eff} , is equal to 1. This represents a state in which the number of fission inducing neutrons in the current generation is equal to the number of fission inducing neutrons in the previous generation. Under normal circumstances, this results in a reactor system with a stable power production due to fission and is generally considered to be steady-state operation of a nuclear reactor. In physical systems, however, reaching and determining a reactor state where $k_{\text{eff}}=1$ represents a challenge due to response time, periodic effects, and reactivity feedback mechanisms among other external factors [1, 2, 3]. Ultimately, this means that if one is trying to assess the state of a reactor either for general operations or criticality based reactor analysis, a methodology must be developed to determine effective critical states over an operations period.

Collecting a subset of critical states becomes further challenging in real systems due to the presence of detector noise in sensors used for the operation of nuclear reactor [4]. In certain cases, noise may lead to cases in which reactor states which are similar appear distinct (that is a case in which noise results in a slightly negative or positive trend over a smaller window of time) or distinct reactor states appear similar (a case in which detector noise makes a positive or negative trend in actual reactor power indistinguishable from critical states). For this reason, a statistics based selection criterion is developed and employed to separate and collect approximate critical states in the Missouri University of Science & Technology Reactor (MSTR) from other non-critical operations or periods of time in which the reactor may appear to be critical while actually exhibiting a positive or negative power trend which cannot be easily determined by operators or analysts.

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Figure 1. MSTR in configuration 134-W.

1.1. MSTR Description and Experiments

MSTR is a research nuclear reactor on the Missouri University of Science & Technology campus in Rolla, Missouri. MSTR is a 200 kW reactor with a neutron spectrum in the thermal regime. MSTR utilizes USi_3 enriched to 19.8 wt% U-235 in an aluminum matrix as curved plates for reactor fuel. Standard fuel assemblies consist of 18 fuel plates surrounded by an aluminum clad and spaced evenly with coolant channels. Light water is used as reactor coolant and moderator. Elements may be moved to different locations on the grid plate at the reactor base to configure the core for experimentation.

In the summer of 2025, MSTR was engaged in research to produce criticality safety benchmarks. In order to effectively assess the reactor at critical, a new configuration (134) was developed and experiments to characterize the reactor core were employed. MSTR in configuration 134 W-mode can be seen in Figure 1.

1.1.1. Characterization Experiments

Three methods for characterizing the reactor core were utilized, consisting of static excess reactivity analysis via critical rod height, reactivity calculation via positive period method, and control-rod drop. These methods were employed to obtain individual control rod worth estimates (including all shim rods and the regulating rod), excess reactivity of the reactor configuration, and reactor shutdown margin.

Control rod drop Control rod drop reactivity estimation was performed by bringing the reactor critical at 600 W and positioning all control rods as follows: the target shim rod was set to a prescribed height, the regulating rod fully removed, and the remaining shim rods are uniformly positioned to maintain criticality. A 120-second stability window was observed to ensure the reactor was in critical state. The electric current to the electromagnet holding the target shim rod was reduced, causing the rod to drop into the core. Reactor power was recorded by reactor operators/experimentalists at 14 seconds and 100 seconds after the target rod was dropped.

Positive period Reactivity calculation by positive period method was performed by measuring the fundamental mode (period) for the Inhour equation of the reactor system [5]. The reactor was brought to critical state at a power level of 10 W. Shim rods were positioned to maintain criticality and for the starting interval of the target rod. For rod tip excess reactivity measurements using the positive period method, the regulating rod remained fully withdrawn for the duration of the experiment while the remaining two shim rods were used for stabilization. A 120-second stability window was observed to ensure the reactor was in critical state. The target control rod was withdrawn until a resulting prompt jump between 30 and 120 seconds was obtained. After 120 seconds elapsed to allow higher order transient modes to decay, reactor power was recorded, and the amount of time elapsed for power to increase

by a given ratio (for all performed measurements, double) was measured. The average reactor period during these transients was between 50 and 400 seconds. The target control rod remained unmoved, while the other shim rods were used to return the reactor to the low power critical state (10 W). The experiment was repeated until the target rod was fully withdrawn.

Excess reactivity via static method Determination of excess reactivity through the static method was performed by calculating the total reactivity worth for all three shim rods via the rod drop method. The total worth of the regulating rod was determined via the positive period method. Differential and integral rod worth tables were constructed for each rod. Critical rod heights were obtained by bringing the reactor critical at 10 W, where the reactivity worth of each rod at its critical height was determined. The sum of the total rod worths minus the critical rod worths was calculated as excess reactivity.

This work examines the production and application of least-squares regression and statistical data analysis based filtering and classification methods to discern approximately critical states captured from the MSTR configuration 134 characterization experiments, as well as establishes a framework for generalized reactor state classification using these methods.

2. METHODOLOGY

The methodology for this analysis is separated by examining data collection and processing methods for both MSTR sensor data and synthetic datasets (section 2.1 and the methods used to filter MSTR data and produce classification thresholds for critical states (section 2.2).

2.1. Data Collection

Data was collected from MSTR core characterization experiments occurring during June and July of 2025. This characterization was performed as required by the MSTR Safety Analysis Report (SAR) due to the implementation of a new reactor core configuration, labeled as configuration 134.

2.1.1. Reactor Power Data Channels

Data was collected over the course of the characterization experiments via radiation detectors near the reactor core. Data from the MSTR power channels needed be pre-processed to be analyzed effectively. To capture more fine effects of reactor power, the linear channel was preferred to the logarithmic channel (the logarithmic channel exhibits increased noise at low power, where fewer reactivity feedback mechanisms are present). Power channels sample at a rate of 8 Hz.

Sensor Data Processing The linear power channel operates on multiple power scales, which can cause a voltage increase resulting in an anomalous reading during transitional periods. These anomalous readings were removed from the dataset by removing the first two data from the complete dataset when a scale change occurred. Scale change information was collected from other MSTR instrumentation.

To ensure the time period in which any observation occurred was normalized the time of each reading was converted to Unix time. This would allow any observation over the course of the experimentation to be accessed independently and allow for regular distinction between any two observation windows.

2.1.2. Simulated Data Production

To determine effective values for filtering methods, simulated data was produced to capture simplified behavior of the reactor system. Equation 1 demonstrates simplified reactor power changes over time with a constant reactivity insertion resulting in a reactor period of τ (s). To produce 'observable' reactor power changes, the relative change in reactor power was adjusted over a 120 second window to examine

similar power effects to those seen by reactor operators as outlined in section 1.1.1. Relative power changes of 10%, 5%, 2%, and 1% over this window were examined. Reactor period can be calculated from this criterion (assuming constant reactivity insertion) by solving Equation 1 for τ resulting in Equation 2 [5].

$$P(t) = P_0 e^{\frac{t}{\tau}} \quad (1)$$

$$\tau = \frac{t}{\ln\left(\frac{P(t)}{P_0}\right)} \quad (2)$$

Reactor period can be either positive or negative, depending on whether power is increasing or decreasing. By solving for $P(t)/P_0$ in 3 two solutions are raised; $P(t)/P_0 = 1.05$ (positive period) and $P(t)/P_0 = 0.95$ (negative period). For each power change percentage, a positive and negative period were calculated to simulate reactor behavior during both power increase and decrease operations. The reactor periods calculated by using this method can be seen in Table I.

$$\left| \frac{P(t)}{P(t) - P_0} \right| = 0.05 \quad (3)$$

Table I. Reactor period power changes over 120 second window.

% change in power	τ (s) [positive period]	τ (s) [negative period]
10	1,260	-1,140
5	2,460	-2,340
2	6,060	-5,940
1	12,060	-11,940
0	∞	$-\infty$

Simulated data was produced using a standard 1/8 second timestep to replicate the behavior of MSTR power channel sampling.

Artificial noise To more effectively mimic MSTR sensor readings, a method to add artificial noise to the simulations was employed. To generate noise, it was assumed that the linear power channel in MSTR produces readings which exist on a normal distribution centered around actual reactor power with a standard deviation of 5% of reactor power ($\sigma = 0.05 * P$) at the time of sampling. An artificial noise vector representing the relative percentage deviation from the power at time of simulation was produced and applied to each simulated dataset.

2.1.3. Noise Reduction

To further reduce the impact on noise in the data on analysis methods, a noise reduction method was employed. A continuous moving average utilizing rolling windows was collected for each datum in the observation window. Windows were centered on the datum being averaged, utilizing the adjacent 4 data in each negative and positive temporal direction. This resulted in a nominal time averaging window of 1.125 seconds, excluding erroneous data that were removed from the original dataset as described in section 2.1.1.

2.2. Filtering and Classification Methods

Classification and filtering methods were developed to collect relevant critical states from the MSTR experimental data.

2.2.1. Classification thresholds

To determine the suitability of an observation as an approximately critical state, a method to produce a classification threshold was developed. From a power perspective, a reactor would be considered absolutely critical if there were no change in reactor power over time, consistent with a period of $\tau = \infty$ or $\tau = -\infty$. This can be analyzed using a first-order least-square regression, in which the first order coefficient (m) satisfies the equation for a line $y = mx + b$. Performing such a regression over a temporal power profile represented by a reactor at critical would result in a first-order regression coefficient of $m = 0$, meaning no change in reactor power with respect to time. Reactors that are not truly critical would exhibit some nonzero change in power over time, resulting in a first-order least-squares solution such that $m \neq 0$, assuming a constant reactivity insertion resulting in a non-infinite stable period. This principle can be used to classify the difference between critical and non-critical system behavior. Furthermore, since nuclear reactors exhibit exponential behavior with respect to power over time, a logarithmic transform of reactor power would result in a linear response assuming stable period. By logarithmically transforming reactor power readings, least-squares regression residuals would ultimately be reduced due to the direct linear behavior of power in the response space.

Due to randomness in noise-enhanced simulated datasets, a range of first-order coefficients exist in a population centered around any constant reactor period. To produce a simple classification threshold, the standard deviation of the population of first-order coefficients from least-squares regression solutions of critical (infinite period) was estimated.

Additionally, to predict the approximate capture rate of non-critical reactor states ($\tau \neq \infty$) the cumulative distribution function of the normal distribution could be used, assuming first-order coefficients centered at the nominal least-squares solution are normally distributed. Using Equation 4, the percentage of solutions existing on the distribution centered on μ within the threshold value x can be calculated [6].

$$\phi\left(\frac{x - \mu}{\sigma}\right) = \frac{1}{2}\left[1 + \operatorname{erf}\left(\frac{x - \mu}{\sigma\sqrt{2}}\right)\right] \quad (4)$$

2.2.2. Additional filtering

While the aforementioned classification threshold could generally filter out critical versus non-critical states, it could fail to detect observations in which reactor power is both increasing and decreasing in the same window. Situations such as this may occur when an operator is attempting to stabilize power, or under the effects of reactivity feedback mechanisms. Specifically, this may result in an observation which has non-linear behavior in the logarithmic response space but a first-order least squares solution where $m \approx 0$. An additional filtering method using least-squares solution residuals was developed to further filter these states.

Since the method of collecting least-squares solution residuals are calculated by squaring the deviation from the predicted value, the sum-of-squares residual represents the magnitude of the deviation. Ultimately, this means that an observation with multiple reactivity insertions would result in non-linear behavior in the logarithmically transformed space and exhibit a larger sum-of-squares residual than an observation with a constant reactivity insertion.

Since not all observations occur at the same reactor power, however, the residuals must be normalized to ensure the residuals from individual observations are comparable. To perform this, an averaged

and normalized residual value could be calculated using Equation 5 in which μ is the mean of the observation window, S_{raw} is the raw sum-of-squares residual for the solution, and n is the number of samples in the observation window (nominally $n = 481$). Since residuals are a measurement of the distance from the expected value, μ^2 functions as a scale normalization factor.

$$S_{norm} = \frac{S_{raw}}{\mu^2 * n} \quad (5)$$

S_{norm} could then be used to compare observations captured within the critical classification threshold described in section 2.2.1, with smaller values of S_{norm} indicating a stronger case for reactor criticality. To produce a metric which could be used to balance performance regarding both criticality and noise reduction, both m and S_{norm} were utilized via equation 6, in which m_{sample} is the first-order coefficient of the regression solution, $m_{threshold}$ is the threshold value, S_{norm}^{sample} is the sample normalized residual, and $S_{norm}^{maximum}$ is the solution population maximum normalized residual. A joint metric was created to ensure that the highest scoring samples represented a high-quality but standard critical event while increasing the score impact of less noisy samples due to the presence of the $S_{norm}^{maximum}$, which captures the noise effects across the complete sample space.

$$score = \left| \frac{m_{sample}}{m_{threshold}} \right| * \frac{S_{norm}^{sample}}{S_{norm}^{maximum}} \quad (6)$$

3. DATA & RESULTS

Positive and negative slope thresholds were calculated to classify the critical states. With a critical noise-enhanced simulated distribution centered around 0.0, positive and negative threshold values of $+/- 1\sigma$ were selected. A standard deviation of $\sigma=1.30e-4$ was found for this distribution, resulting in a positive and negative threshold of $+/-1.30e-4$. Table II shows the capture rate of samples from the simulated power distributions using thresholds. Figure 2 illustrates the distributions with the most significant capture rates using thresholds. Each distribution contains 100,000 noise-enhanced power simulations.

Table II. Simulated power distributions threshold capture rate.

Power change %	$\mu (m)$	Sample capture rate (%)
+10%	7.94e-4	0.00%
-10%	-8.78e-4	0.00%
+5%	4.07e-4	0.00%
-5%	-4.27e-4	0.00%
+2%	1.65e-4	6.41%
-2%	-1.68e-4	5.50%
+1%	8.29e-5	39.4%
-1%	-8.38e-5	38.8%

Thresholds were then applied to MSTR data. To reflect the appropriate population of critical states valid for experimentation, linear channel readings smaller than 5 W were removed from the dataset. From the characterization experiments, 478,914 possible 60 second windows were collected. Using threshold selection 188,328 possible critical states were classified. This results in a 39.3% collection rate from the valid experiment set. Due to the nature of reactor operations, this capture rate is reasonable (as the reactor is mostly operated at approximately critical, with power changes primarily to reach a new steady state).

Figure 2. Simulated first-order coefficient distributions with classification threshold.

After sample windows were collected using the classification threshold and compared using calculated S_{norm} values, observations could be transformed back into the linear space to depict actual MSTR behavior. Figure 3 shows the 60 second window of MSTR linear power channel readings within classification thresholds exhibiting the smallest S_{norm} . The highest performing sample can be seen in Figure 3. The least-squares solution in the log space resulted in a first-order coefficient of $m = 3.43e - 10$ and a normalized residual of $S_{norm} = 1.02e - 7$. This implies highly stable reactor power with minimal noise compared to other possible candidates.

Figure 3. Highest performing 60 second window including logarithmically transformed data with least-squares solution (top) and original MSTR processed recorder data (bottom).

4. CONCLUSIONS

A method to filter approximately critical states in nuclear reactors over 60 second windows using power channels was developed. Thresholds were produced via statistical analysis to distinguish between

reactor periods, assuming periodic effects exist on a normal distribution. Classification thresholds of $\pm 1.3e-4 m$ were determined, resulting in a 60 second window capture rate of 39.3% of all candidates from MSTR characterization experimentation. A normalized residual from least-squares solutions was combined with the first-order regression coefficient to develop a scoring metric to determine sample quality. The highest performing sample found resulted in a first-order regression coefficient of $m=3.43e-10$ and a normalized residual of $S_{norm}=1.02e-7$.

Future work would include an expansion of regression-based classification methods to include non-critical reactor states. Additionally, further development of statistical methods could be analyzed to create a generalized method for estimating the statistical confidence of a reactor state as approximately critical for MSTR or similar systems under operation with minimal reactivity feedback.

NOMENCLATURE

k_{eff}	Effective multiplication factor
μ	Mean
σ	Standard deviation
τ	Reactor period (s)
m	First-order linear regression coefficient
S_{norm}	Normalized sum-of-squares residual

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